

Me, my robot, and our job

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

There is a general fear of AI and its impact on society, but it could be suggested a morality exists within AI that rests outside of the general perception of AI functionality. As robots and AI become more capable, what will this mean for the job market, and how humans function within a world where we may be working alongside robots in the workplace? How do emotionally intelligent robots fit into the human creative process?

2. Aim

To discuss morality within AI and suggest a future with robotic coworkers

3. Keywords

Robotics, AI, Pepper, emotion, morality

Author biography

Sean McKelvey Sean McKelvey has a background in contemplative psychology, and has spent the past 13 year living in Japan. Sean currently designs and creates innovative digital products at BCG Digital Ventures. Previously, Sean helped to create the world's first mass-produced emotional companion robot, Pepper.

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